

COMPONENTS OF LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

This thesis highlights the concept of linguistic competence as a fundamental component of effective English language teaching, particularly in the preparation of prospective teachers. It argues that competence is not only synonymous with knowledge but also represents a combination of knowledge, skills, abilities, and attitudes required for successful task performance. In the context of teaching, linguistic competence involves both mastery of language systems and the ability to apply them appropriately in real communicative situations. Drawing on theoretical perspectives, including those of Noam Chomsky, the study highlights the evolution of linguistic competence from a focus on internalized grammatical knowledge to a broader communicative and functional understanding.

KEY WORDS

Linguistic competence, knowledge, skills, teaching techniques, grammatical competence, lexical competence, phonological competence, semantic competence.

The term "competence" cannot be a synonym of knowledge, as it is a combination of knowledge, skills, abilities, and attitude that helps a person performs a task successfully. As for teachers, the term "competence" means knowing a skill or knowledge, and explaining it to students. Linguistic competence is considered as a main element of effective English language teaching, especially in the preparation of prospective teachers. Besides its basic definition as knowledge of grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation, it also involves the ability to use language flexibly and appropriately in real communicative situations. For future teachers, this competence is not only theoretical but also practical, as they are expected to model accurate language use in the classroom and respond to learners' needs in real time.

According to theoretical views, linguistic competence is often linked to the ideas of Noam Chomsky, who introduced the concept to describe a speaker's internalized knowledge of language rules. Nevertheless, in modern language teaching, this concept has expanded to include functional and communicative aspects. This means that teachers must not only know the rules of the language but also understand how these rules operate in authentic communication. As a result, linguistic competence is closely associated with teaching techniques.

Components of linguistic competence include grammatical competence, lexical competence, phonological competence, semantic competence. Grammatical competence is considered the primary competence of linguistic competence. To obtain grammatical competence, a teacher must gain the knowledge of syntax, morphology, rules of sentence formation. Without grammar competence, students cannot express themselves in both spoken and written language. No grammar means no meaning. Even in reading and listening tasks, grammar knowledge is vital to understand the meaning of a sentence.

Vocabulary is the main source of any language. Knowledge of vocabulary and its usage in different contexts are considered lexical competence. When the teacher is aware of lexical competence, she can explain her students how to use words correctly in different contexts. An

English teacher with a rich vocabulary can express her ideas more clearly to her students. When she teaches a topic, she can easily show examples to support students' understanding.

Phonological competence plays a vital role in English language teaching. This competence aids teachers teach their students how to produce correct sounds and recognize them. Teachers with good pronunciation skills can module their students to pronounce sounds accurately. If the teacher can module correctly, students produce sounds accurately. If not, they may adapt the way their teachers taught. It will encourage fossilized errors in pronunciation.

To understand something is important in every language. Conveying meaning is essential to the speaker. Since, it is important to explain his ideas clearly to the listener. The ability to interpret words, phrases and sentences is considered semantic competence. With the help of this competence, the teacher can teach her students how to use words accurately in real-life situations.

Integrating linguistic competence with pedagogical skills is crucial. Teachers who obtain strong linguistic knowledge but lack the ability to explain or demonstrate it may struggle in the classroom. Therefore, linguistic competence should be developed alongside teaching methodologies, classroom management skills, and the ability to adapt language input according to learners' proficiency levels. For example, a teacher should be able to simplify complex grammatical structures or paraphrase vocabulary depending on students' understanding.

Competence is more than knowledge. It includes knowledge and skills. All linguistic competence is vital in English teaching. Each one has its own role in teaching and learning English. If the teacher is knowledgeable, she knows the information, but she also needs methods to explain her ideas. Therefore, being a well-educated teacher is not enough. She also must be aware of different methods so that she can convey her meaning to others. Giving just information is not teaching. Students can read any information from internet. So, teachers should collect information, organize, and enrich them in order to teach their students. For example, if they want to teach collocations, they, firstly, have to search for information about collocations. Then, they must select some collocations related to the topic, and find their meaning. After that, they have to make up some sentences with collocations. The last step is the most important one. At this step, teachers have to think about teaching collocations to students. It is difficult, as each learner obtains different level of understanding, and learning pace. It is time to perform the teacher's ability. Everyone can learn, but teach. Gaining language competence is crucial for future English teachers. They have to teach students in different language, not their mother tongue. It can sometimes be difficult, as students may not know the information in their own language. If they know, it will be easier to explain them. If not, the teacher should show her abilities to explain her students. In other words, without practical methodology, being a well-rounded teacher is not enough. As its name, a teacher should teach, not to find information, and give them to students.

In today's world, a teacher with linguistic competence can get well-paid job, since they are knowledgeable, and able to teach what they know accurately to students. Therefore, they can reach their goals rather than well-educated teachers. Teaching is like a business. If it is competent to others, it can be sold easily, as everyone wants to purchase a product with a lot of qualities. Thus, being a teacher with linguistic competence is important in order to be a component teacher. Modern technologies have created new opportunities for enhancing linguistic competence. Online platforms, language learning applications, and digital resources

provide access to a wide range of materials and interactive activities. These tools support autonomous learning and allow prospective teachers to practice language skills outside the classroom environment.

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